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**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF VIDEO – ASSISTED WORKTEXT
(VAW) IN PHYSICS 10**

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this study was to provide relevant learning materials that can satisfy the pressing need for education by developing and validating a Video-Assisted Worktext (VAW) in Physics. The content of the VAW was based on the least mastered competency of the Regional Midyear Assessment (RMYA) year 2023.

There were three participant groups in the study. The first group of participants included seven expert validators. They evaluated the VAW in terms of its content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and other findings if any. The second group of participants included forty (40) students not under the supervision of the researcher for pilot testing before implementation. The third group of participants included forty (40) students handled by the researcher who served as the study's subjects to determine whether the activities and lesson content in the VAW were adequate based on how well they performed on the pretest test.

The study made use of one group pretest-posttest design. The researcher used the prescribed evaluation tool for Non-Printed Resources of the Department of Education. Based on the results from the experts, the developed Video-Assisted Worktext in Physics 10 met all the criteria found in each parameter on the evaluation tool for non-printed resources. After the intervention, the students' scores significantly increased.

From there, it was recommended that the developed VAW be used as an additional learning opportunity, given that the concepts presented in the printed materials were expanded upon through video lessons. The material, which was anchored to the analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation (ADDIE) model may serve as a prototype for the development of worktext and other instructional materials.

KEYWORDS: *Video-Assisted, Worktext, Mirrors and Lenses, Least mastered competency*

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INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a key medium for achieving institutional goals such as improving students' knowledge and skills by engaging them in various learning activities that prepare them for the future. Students understand information in numerous ways. Some learn visually, while others learn best audibly or kinesthetically. Charts, graphs, and pictures help visual learners learn by providing visual cues. Reading and listening to lectures, educational videos, and tutorials are both beneficial for auditory learners. Kinesthetic learners pick things up by doing and applying what they learned.

The Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations are to ensure inclusive quality education and promote continuous and lifelong learning opportunities for all. For this to happen, the fourth Sustainable Goal on Education (SDG 4) should be put into practice. The Video-Assisted Worktext (VAW) in Physics 10 enhanced the quality of Education by engaging the students with interactive activities which ensures that no one will be left behind.

The theory of experiential learning, introduced by David Kolb (2014), highlights the significance of acquiring knowledge through direct experience and reflection. Worktexts can integrate experiential learning by presenting real-life scenarios, simulations, and problem-solving tasks, requiring learners to apply their knowledge in practical situations. According to Selga (2015), worktexts serve the purpose of keeping one student engaged while another is being attended to. Her study affirmed the validity of the proposed worktext, and she concluded that worktexts play a role in achieving specific subject objectives while offering activities that contribute to the development of higher cognitive skills. This idea supported the development of the VAW as it contains the type of activities like fill-in-the-blank and other challenging activities.

The systemic gaps are still being regularly addressed given the situation in the Philippines. As part of the reform plan for Quality Basic Education, the Philippines became a member of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Programme for International Assessment (PISA) is being conducted by the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) every three years. This evaluates the academic achievement across nations that are part of the assessment in the subjects of Science, Math, and Reading. The Philippines took part in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) for the first time in the year 2018. The findings revealed that Filipino 15-year-olds were on the lower end of the rankings among 78 countries and territories (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2019).

In line with the above study, based on the data and results from the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), last December 5, 2023, they indicated that there were no notable advancements, improvements, and changes in the academic performance of Filipino students in the abovementioned subject.

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The Philippines still ranked the lowest which is at fifth. Compared to 2018, the proportion of students scoring below the baseline level of proficiency (Level 2) did not change significantly. This shows that teachers need to understand, be good, and be wise at choosing different teaching methods and strategies that will help them achieve their goals of making every student globally competitive in all subject areas (Brown, 2019).

The researcher encountered the above-mentioned studies and drew inspiration from her teaching experience in Grade 10 Physics. This prompted her to develop a material aimed at simplifying the learning of physics for students, which is the VAW. The topics included in the VAW were from the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Having been announced by the Department of Education, MELCs shall continue to be applied in the School Year 2022-2023.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter focused on the research design, respondents, population and samples, research instrument, and the statistical treatment needed for reliable data analysis and interpretation.

Research Design

Initially, the study made use of Research and Development Design. The updated Frascati Manual (7th Edition., OECD 2015) defines R&D design. According to them, it is a method of investigation where it is assumed that new scientific knowledge is discovered due to a series of linear and sequential stages that consist of Basic Research and Development.

The current study also utilized the design which is the *one-group pretest-posttest design*. The pretest was done before the group got the treatment so the pretest could represent the group's initial ability. The treatment here is the implementation of VAW to the group. The posttest was conducted after the group received treatment so that the posttest could represent the group's final ability.

Data Gathering Procedures

To develop the VAW, the researcher used the ADDIE model which stands for Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. One of the approaches that recommends the general, methodical, dynamic, and adaptable process of instructional design for learning effectively is called ADDIE Model (Holden, 2015).

Phase 1 - Analysis/Preparation: In the analysis and preparation stage, the researcher examined the learning gaps to ensure the effectiveness of the VAW. A letter asking for permission to conduct a study was sent to the Schools Division and to be signed by the School Division Superintendent. Also, a permission letter was sent to the school principal to seek approval to have some of the students of DJGHS as

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participants in the study. A consent letter to the parents was distributed upon the conduct of the study. This was followed by the collection of least mastered competencies in the Regional Mid – year Assessment for the School year 2022 – 2023 and served as the justification basis for developing the material.

Phase II – Design: The researcher used the gathered data and information in the analysis phase. The researcher planned, organized, and designed the format of the material, wrote the lesson applications, assessments, and enrichments, and finalized the script and content of the video, layout, and design of the worktext. It has also undergone a comprehensive evaluation process which will contribute to the improvement of the VAW.

Phase III – Development: The researcher started to develop the VAW. Science and educational technology experts evaluated the VAW according to the set criteria to be found on *LRMDS Evaluation Rating Sheet for Non-Printed Materials*". Final revisions made and suggested by the experts were incorporated.

Phase IV – Implementation: The developed VAW was implemented among the third group of participants which is the forty (40) heterogenous students handled by the researcher. After the implementation, data was gathered. The VAW was implemented in 4 weeks, almost 1 (one) month.

Phase V – Evaluation: The researcher assessed the effectiveness of the developed VAW which involved gathering feedback and data to achieve the desired goals and outcomes.

Scope and Delimitation

This study attempted to develop and validate a Video-Assisted Worktext (VAW) in teaching Physics 10 addressing least-learned competencies in Quarter 2 of the School Year 2023-2024. Through RMYA, DepEd will determine the most learned and least learned competencies as well as the extent of the cognitive levels of students.

Based on the teacher's report on the result of the Regional Mid-year assessment for the school year 2022-2023, the least learned competency is *predicting the qualitative characteristics (orientation, type, and magnification) of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses (S10FE-IIg-50 and S10FE-IIg-51)*. This competency served as the basis for developing the VAW.

The VAW was divided into two (2) parts which contain two (2) lessons, a total of 4 lessons. There were three groups of participants.

The *first group* of participants was composed of (5) five content experts and (2) Educational Technology experts. The role is to evaluate the VAW across various factors.

Pilot testing of the material was conducted among the *second group* of participants which involved forty (40) heterogenous Grade 10 students not under the researcher's supervision. The pretest-posttest materials undergone item analysis to determine the difficulty index and discrimination index of each item.

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To verify the effectiveness of the VAW, it undergone implementation to the third group of participants, which consisted of forty (40) Grade 10 heterogenous students handled by the researcher. The result of the post- test became an indicator of the effectiveness of the developed instructional material.

In determining the effectiveness of the VAW, mean and standard deviation were employed to verify the expert results. This methodology facilitated the assessment of the extent of variation present in the dataset and provided insights regarding the standard deviation of each criterion from the mean for the expert's validation checklist. Also, Shapiro-Wilk Test and Wilcoxon Signed Test Results statistical test was used to assess whether the given sample of data comes from a normally distributed population. Moreover, the comparison of the pre-test and post-test scores was tested using Wilcoxon signed rank test, the non-parametric counterpart of the t-test for a dependent sample is more appropriate for analyzing the data and improvement of scores if it is statistically significant.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this study was to develop and validate a Video-Assisted Worktext (VAW) for Grade 10 Physics. Particularly, the researcher fulfilled the following objectives:

1. Develop a Video-Assisted Worktext in Physics 10.
2. Validate the Video – Assisted Worktext in Physics for Grade 10 along the

following:

- 2.1 Experts' evaluation of the VAW in terms of:

- 2.1.1 Content Quality
- 2.1.2 Instructional Quality
- 2.1.3 Technical Quality
- 2.1.4 Other Findings

- 2.2 End user's evaluation using Pre-test and Posttest

3. Know the significant difference between the pretest and posttest of the end users.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the participants.

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Factors	Average Rating	Min. and Max. Points	Remarks
Content Quality	39.00	<i>Min:</i> 30.00 <i>Max:</i> 40.00	Passed
Instructional Quality	39.00	<i>Min:</i> 30.00 <i>Max:</i> 40.00	Passed
Technical Quality	50.00	<i>Min:</i> 39.00 <i>Max:</i> 52.00	Passed
Other Findings	16.00	<i>Min:</i> 16.00 <i>Max:</i> 16.00	Passed

RESULTS

This section presented the statistical information, data analysis, and interpretation obtained through the research process.

Table 1. Ratings from the Experts' Validation of the VAW

The evaluators examined and rated the material based on the evaluation instruments to which the resource meets the criteria. The table shows that the VAW passed all the criteria.

The findings strongly supported the study of Robles and Acedo (2019) that the video tutorials which they have developed attained a great extent of validity. The experts in their study evaluated the educational videos as highly acceptable and highly relevant. In this present study, the experts evaluated the VAW as very satisfactory.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics on Pre-test and Posttest

The mean score is the average performance of the group. The mean score

	Pretest	Posttest
N	40	40
Mean	13.9	38.9
Standard deviation	4.65	3.74

increased substantially from 13.9 in the pretest to 38.9 in the posttest, indicating that there is an improvement in students' performance. Standard deviation measures the dispersion or spread of data points around the mean. In this case, the standard deviation decreased from 4.65 in the pretest to 3.74 in the posttest. This tighter clustering around the mean indicates greater consistency or stability in performance among the participants after whatever intervention or treatment occurred between the pretest and posttest.

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Pretest Median	Posttest Median	z	p	Interpretation
13.00	39.30	-5.52	.000	Reject Null hypothesis

Table 3. *Wilcoxon Signed Ranked Test on the Pretest and Post-test*

A Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted to determine whether the observed improvement in test scores was statistically significant. The test produced a z-score of -5.52 and a p-value of $.000$. The negative z-score indicates that the post-test scores were significantly higher than the pre-test scores. The p-value of $.000$ is less than the typical significance level of $.05$, indicating strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis and can be concluded that there is significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the participants.

DISCUSSION

Based on the table and results of the pretest and posttest, the Video-assisted worktext has proven to be highly effective in enhancing the learning experience and improving students' performance and comprehension. The integration of video-assisted worktexts has led to significant improvements in students' understanding and retention of academic content, offering a dynamic and multimedia-rich learning environment.

Since the effectiveness of the VAW has been proven and tested, teachers should incorporate this material and strategy into their classes to maintain quality education in all modes of learning delivery.

Conclusion

Video-assisted worktexts served as a powerful tool for enhancing the learning experience, as evidenced by the notable improvements in students' performance and comprehension. The integration of VAW has demonstrated significant effectiveness among students, fostering improved understanding and retention of academic content. It has proven to be an effective pedagogical approach, offering students a dynamic and multimedia-rich learning environment. The VAW holds the attention of the students. The length of the video material was also suitable for the student's screen time limit. With easy-to-understand printed material linked to video lessons and interactive assessments, students' assessment performance improved considerably.

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Recommendations

Since the effectiveness of the VAW has been proven and tested, teachers should incorporate this material and strategy into their classes to maintain the quality education in all modes of learning delivery. The VAW that was developed by the researcher may be adopted and utilized by other science teachers to improve the performance of the learners. To guarantee the quality of learning resources, teachers should consider all the criteria or indicators outlined in the evaluation tool employed in this study. School Administrators may create an instructional evaluation guideline as basis for schools in developing instructional materials before the actual usage by the students. Researchers may conduct another study like the present study which may also develop other kinds of instructional materials that will help improve the performances of the learners.

REFERENCES

- Akporobaro, O. W., Odunayo, A. J., & Onyinye, I. M. (2020). Availability of Instructional Materials and Interest of Secondary School Students in the Study of Physics in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Technology and Humanities*, 1(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.53797/jthkss.v1i2.1.2020>
- Salavaria, F., Galicia, D. C., Mandligod, R. P., Mariano, J. B., Escartin, M. N., & Canare, E. D. (2014). *Development and validation of worktext in statistics*.
- Garin, M. (2022a). Worktext as supplemental material in improving mathematics' performance of grade 9 students. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 105(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp1001051720223656>
- Garin, M. (2022b). Worktext as supplemental material in improving mathematics' performance of grade 9 students. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 105(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp1001051720223656>
- Assem, H. D., Nartey, L., Appiah, E., & Aidoo, J. K. (2023). A Review of Students' Academic Performance in Physics: Attitude, Instructional Methods, Misconceptions and Teachers Qualification. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(1), 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2023.4.1.551>
- Casildo, N. J. G., Aguirre, M. R. C., Bonifacio, K. L. A., Ayunar, G. S., Escarlos, G. S., & Wenceslao, R. C. (2023). A Decision Support System for Predicting Students' Performance in the National Achievement Test (NAT) of Senior High School Students (pp. 178–190). https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-056-5_20

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- Dejarlo, J. O. (2022). *Development and validation of worktext in basic calculus*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8FYN9>
- Diate, K., & Claire Mordeno, I. V. (n.d.). All rights reserved. In *Asia Research Network Journal of Education* (Vol. 1, Issue 2).
- Dusabimana, J., & Rugema Leon, M. (2022). *Challenges in Teaching Physics using Inquiry-Based Teaching and Learning Approach: A Case of Lower Secondary School in Gakenke District, Rwanda*. *East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 3(3), 140–146. <https://doi.org/10.4314/eajess.v3i3.188>
- Isma'il, A., & Lukman, O. M. (2022). *Availability and Utilization of Instructional Materials in Teaching and Learning of Biology in Senior Secondary Schools*. *Aquademia*, 6(2), ep22013. <https://doi.org/10.30935/aquademia/12614>
- Kulgemeyer, C., Hörnlein, M., & Sterzing, F. (2022). *Exploring the effects of physics explainer videos and written explanations on declarative knowledge and the illusion of understanding*. *International Journal of Science Education*, 44(11), 1855–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2022.2100507>
- Ou, C., Joyner, D. A., & Goel, A. K. (2019). *Designing and developing video lessons for online learning: A seven-principle model*. *Online Learning Journal*, 23(2), 82–104. <https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v23i2.1449>
- Padua, S. S., & Cascolan, H. M. (n.d.). *Development and Validation of a Multimedia Based-Module in Science for TVL Track introduction Teaching serves as an important medium for achieving institutional goals of enhancing*.
- Rogayan, D. V., & Dollete, L. F. (2019). *Development and Validation of Physical Science Workbook for Senior High School*. *Science Education International*, 30(4), 284–290. <https://doi.org/10.33828/sei.v30.i4.5>

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